

Hormone Therapy is Associated with Decreased Risk of Running Away Among Transgender Adolescents.

By TRAVIS CAMPBELL AND AND YANA VAN DER MEULEN RODGERS*

Transgender individuals in the United States face pervasive stigma, discrimination, and violence (Carpenter, Eppink and Gonzales, 2020). These experiences contribute to gender minority stress and gender dysphoria, both of which contribute to poor physical and mental health outcomes among transgender populations (Dolotina and Turban, 2022). These outcomes include substantially higher rates of depression, anxiety, and suicidal behavior compared to individuals whose gender identity aligns with their assigned sex at birth (Dhejne et al., 2018). The primary intervention for gender dysphoria is gender-affirming care (GAC), which encompasses puberty suppression, gender-affirming hormone therapy (GAHT), and surgical procedures, along with social and legal affirmation. Among trans adolescents, GAHT is sometimes introduced after puberty suppression when they are ready to begin gender-affirming physical changes. Unlike blockers, which only delay changes, GAHT actively promotes congruence, reducing dysphoria and associated risks like depression and suicidality. Surgical interventions are rarely performed in adolescence, making GAHT the most impactful component of GAC for this age group.

Bolstering the welfare of transgender youth matters not only for individual wellbeing, it also matters for society at large and the macroeconomy (Badgett, Waaldijk and Rodgers, 2019). In a politically charged environment, making the case for providing transgender youth with access to GAHT entails not only moral suasion but also credible evidence that receiving GAHT has meaningful beneficial effects.

There is very little quantitative evidence on the effects of GAHT on measures of mental health and wellbeing among transgender youth. One exception is Campbell et al. (2023), which

used the US Transgender Survey (USTS) and rigorous econometric techniques to show that uptake of GAHT is associated with a 5.7 percentage point reduction in the risk of attempting suicide. While attempting suicide is a critical marker of well-being among transgender youth, it is not the sole indicator; behaviors such as running away also signal severe distress. Risk factors for running away include depression, lack of family and community support, and victimization, and the act of running away increases the subsequent risk of drug addiction, homelessness, sexual risk taking, dropping out of school, criminal activity, and additional depressive symptoms (Thompson and Pillai, 2006; Tucker et al., 2011).

This paper uses the USTS to provide new evidence on the association between GAHT initiation and the risk of running away among transgender youth. Our event study approach compares youths who started GAHT (treated group) with those who initiated GAHT a year later (control group). Results indicate that GAHT is associated with a 2 percentage point reduction in the risk of running away from home, which amounts to a 20 percent decrease in the risk of running away relative to the pretreatment mean. Moreover, the effect is largest when GAHT began at younger ages (i.e., 14–15).

I. Data Description and Methodology

A. 2015 United States Transgender Survey

Our analysis draws on the 2015 U.S. Transgender Survey (USTS), a large nonrandom online survey of 27,715 transgender adults ages 18 and older from all fifty states, the District of Columbia, U.S. territories, and U.S. military bases abroad. The USTS provides extensive information on education, employment, health, family life, gender identity development, and access to healthcare. Another wave was collected in 2022 by the Advocates for Trans Equality (formerly the National Center for Transgender

* Campbell: Southern Oregon University (email: campbelt1@sou.edu). Rodgers: Rutgers University (email: Yana.rodgers@rutgers.edu). The project received IRB approval from Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey (Study ID: Pro2021000636).

Equality) but as of December 2025 the data had still not been released.

The survey records the respondent’s age at key life events, enabling the construction of a retrospective panel. Respondents are asked, “Have you ever had any of the health care listed below for your gender identity or gender transition?” If they respond yes to the option for “Hormone Treatment/HRT,” respondents are also asked the age at which they began GAHT. We use this question to define the treatment indicator, which equals one in the year GAHT began and in all subsequent years, and zero in all prior years.

To measure the outcome of interest, running away, we use information from the following questions: “Did you ever run away from home because you are trans?” If the answer is yes, respondents are asked “At what age did you run away from home because you are trans?”. We use these responses to construct an indicator that equals zero until the year of first running away and one thereafter. Because this question is asked only of respondents “who have some, most, or all immediate family members who know they are trans,” our analysis focuses on this subgroup.

The USTS includes similar retrospective questions for attempting suicide, undergoing conversion therapy, receiving puberty blockers, and several gender-identity milestones (e.g., first feeling one’s gender differed from assigned sex, first thinking of oneself as trans, first disclosure to others, and living full time in one’s gender). We use these time-varying measures as potential controls.

Our final sample includes 1,101 respondents who began GAHT between ages 14 and 18, whose families were aware of their transgender identity, and have nonmissing data from the control variables. Note the USTS is a nonrandom sample. Comparisons with randomly sampled transgender adults in the Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System show that USTS respondents tend to be younger, less racially diverse, and more affluent (Shannon, 2022). As a result, the analysis may not reflect the broader transgender population.

B. Methodology

To estimate the association between GAHT and running away among transgender adoles-

cents, we compare changes in running away for youth who begin GAHT between ages 14 and 17 with those who initiate GAHT one year later. This event-study approach assumes that the precise age of GAHT initiation is unrelated to other factors that could also affect the likelihood of running away from home.

In our retrospective panel, the analysis sample is a “stack” of four cohorts defined by the age at which respondents initiated GAHT, from ages 14 through 17. Within each cohort, the treated group includes those who began GAHT at that specific age, while the control group consists of individuals who initiated one year later; respondents who start GAHT at age 18 appear only as controls. For each cohort, the event window spans the five years before and one year after the treated group’s initiation age, and event time is aligned accordingly, ranging from -5 to 0 .

To avoid overly small samples, individuals within each cohort may be born in different calendar years, as long as they are the same age relative to the GAHT initiation event. To account for these differences, the regression includes both cohort-age and cohort-calendar-year fixed effects. Within each cohort, we also apply synthetic unit weights to balance the outcome between treated and control individuals over the five years preceding GAHT initiation (Arkhangelsky et al., 2021).

We use stacked regression with cohort-specific dynamic treatment effects. We test for selection bias by allowing the trends in outcomes to deviate between treated and control individuals for five years prior to GAHT. The baseline specification is:

$$(1) \quad Y_{c,i,t} = \mu + \sum_{k=-5}^0 \sum_{c=1}^4 \beta_{k,c} D_{k,c,i,t} + X'_{c,i,t} \kappa + \alpha_{c,i} + \delta_{c,t} + \gamma_{c,y} + \varepsilon_{c,i,t}$$

where Y denotes an indicator for person i of cohort c ever running away as of event-time t , $D_{k,c}$ are cohort-specific leads and lags of an indicator variable for GAHT, X is a vector of cohort-specific controls for receipt of puberty blockers, exposure to conversion therapy, and gender-identity milestones in case they are concurrent, $\alpha_{c,i}$ are cohort-specific individual fixed effects, $\delta_{c,t}$ are cohort-specific event time fixed effects, $\gamma_{c,y}$ are cohort-specific calendar year fixed ef-

fects, and $\varepsilon_{c,i,t}$ is the error term. The regression is weighted by the cohort-specific synthetic unit weights. Standard errors are clustered at the individual level, the level at which the treatment occurs. The main identifying assumption is parallel trends in the outcome.

The above specification avoids the bias that arises in difference in differences with staggered adoption by ensuring that each cohort uses only clean, not-yet-treated controls. It also prevents the incoherent aggregation of cohort-specific effects that can occur in stacked fixed-effects models with a single treatment indicator by estimating cohort-specific treatment indicators (Wing, Freedman and Hollingsworth, 2024).

We use two ways to average the cohort-specific estimates. First, we present a weighted average, where each cohort is weighted by its share of treated individuals; this reflects the average association between initiating GAHT and running away for those who actually begin treatment. Second, we present an unweighted average across cohorts, which may be more clinically relevant if the effects of starting earlier in adolescence are of interest. Because most individuals initiate GAHT later (around half at age 17), the weighted average places greater emphasis on the older cohorts, while the unweighted average treats all cohorts equally.

If the timing of GAHT initiation is quasi-random, treated and control groups should appear similar before treatment. Supplemental Appendix Table A.1 shows no meaningful imbalance in respondents' race, region of birth, sex assigned at birth, or history of suicide attempts. There are differences in gender-identity development, use of puberty blockers, and exposure to conversion therapy, so we include these variables as controls in the regression analysis. Importantly, the share of respondents who ran away from home before starting GAHT is similar across groups, and we later show that trends in this outcome are parallel over the five years preceding initiation. Nevertheless, these observed imbalances warrant interpreting the estimated effects as associations rather than strictly causal.

II. Event Study Results

Table 1 presents the event-study estimates for the association between GAHT initiation and

running away during the first year of treatment among transgender adolescents. The table reports cohort-specific estimates and both aggregation methods. Figures 1a and 1b present the corresponding event-study plots.

The estimates suggest that earlier initiation of GAHT is associated with larger reductions in the likelihood of running away compared to initiation at later ages. Starting GAHT at age 14 is linked to an 8.39 percentage-point decline (SE = 4.64) in the probability of running away during the first year. The association declines steadily with later initiation ages: 3.37 percentage points at age 15 (SE = 2.10), 2.43 points at age 16 (SE = 2.09), and 0.74 points at age 17 (SE = 1.56). Given the small size of each cohort, none of the cohort-specific estimates reach conventional 95% statistical significance.

Although early initiation of GAHT may reduce the likelihood of running away, the estimated effects for the youngest cohorts are implausibly large and likely overstate any direct impact of GAHT. At age 14, for example, the estimated effect corresponds to a 96% reduction relative to the share who had run away prior to treatment—an unrealistic magnitude. This reflects both the very small size of the age-14 cohort and the rarity of running away, which make the estimate highly sensitive to sampling variation. Of the 23 individuals who began GAHT at age 14, only two had run away before treatment, none of the remaining 21 ran away during the first year of GAHT, and a few individuals in the comparison group ran away at age 14, thus generating the outsized estimate. With a larger cohort, it is almost certain that at least one youth initiating GAHT would run away, substantially reducing the estimated effect. These cohort-specific results should therefore be interpreted with abundant caution.

Since most respondents in the sample begin GAHT later in adolescence, averaging the estimates across cohorts according to the share of the treated individuals yields a modest association of -1.97 percentage points (SE = 1.11), a 20.4% reduction relative to the pre-GAHT run-away rate of 9.68 percent. In contrast, the unweighted average, which gives equal weight to all cohorts and places relatively more emphasis on earlier initiation ages, produces a large and precise estimate of -3.73 percentage points (SE = 1.43), representing a substantial 38.5% reduc-

tion relative to the same baseline. These large associations likely reflect not only GAHT but also the broader effects of coming out and receiving family support.

Both Figures 1a and 1b show a sharp decline in the probability of running away during the first year of GAHT. They also show parallel pre-treatment trends between treated and control individuals during the five years preceding initiation, thus supporting the validity of the parallel-trends assumption.

III. Conclusion

This study has used the 2015 US Transgender Survey to estimate the relationship between the initiation of hormone therapy and the risk of running away from home among transgender adolescents. We constructed a retrospective panel of transgender youth and employed an event study design. We found that GAHT is associated with a meaningful reduction in the risk that a transgender adolescent will try to run away from home. The average association between GAHT and the risk of running away is a decrease of 2 percentage points, which constitutes a 20% decrease relative to the baseline rate of running away. These associations are largest when GAHT occurs at a young age.

Although we are constrained by some formidable data and methodology limitations (especially the challenge of small sample sizes for the youngest age cohorts), we believe that the event study estimates provide compelling evidence of the beneficial effects of GAHT. This evidence comes at a time when states are increasingly restricting access to GAHT and gender-affirming care for transgender youth. Policymakers and healthcare professionals need to recognize that such restrictions can elevate the risk of running away and substantially undermine the mental health and overall well-being of transgender adolescents.

REFERENCES

- Arkhangelsky, Dmitry, Susan Athey, David A Hirshberg, Guido W Imbens, and Stefan Wager.** 2021. "Synthetic difference-in-differences." *American Economic Review*, 111(12): 4088–4118.
- Badgett, MV Lee, Kees Waaldijk, and Yana van der Meulen Rodgers.** 2019. "The relationship between LGBT inclusion and economic development: Macro-level evidence." *World Development*, 120: 1–14.
- Campbell, Travis, Samuel Mann, Duc Hien Nguyen, and Yana van der Meulen Rodgers.** 2023. "Hormone therapy, suicidal risk, and transgender youth in the United States." Vol. 113, 551–555, American Economic Association 2014 Broadway, Suite 305, Nashville, TN 37203.
- Carpenter, Christopher S, Samuel T Eppink, and Gilbert Gonzales.** 2020. "Transgender status, gender identity, and socioeconomic outcomes in the United States." *ILR Review*, 73(3): 573–599.
- Dhejne, Cecilia, Roy Van Vlerken, Gunter Heylens, and Jon Arcelus.** 2018. "Mental health and gender dysphoria: A review of the literature." *Gender Dysphoria and Gender Incongruence*, 56–69.
- Dolotina, Brett, and Jack L Turban.** 2022. "A multipronged, evidence-based approach to improving mental health among transgender and gender-diverse youth." *JAMA Network Open*, 5(2): e220926–e220926.
- Shannon, Matthew.** 2022. "The labour market outcomes of transgender individuals." *Labour Economics*, 77: 102006.
- Thompson, Sanna J, and Vijayan K Pillai.** 2006. "Determinants of runaway episodes among adolescents using crisis shelter services." *International Journal of Social Welfare*, 15(2): 142–149.
- Tucker, Joan S, Maria Orlando Edelen, Phyllis L Ellickson, and David J Klein.** 2011. "Running away from home: A longitudinal study of adolescent risk factors and young adult outcomes." *Journal of youth and adolescence*, 40(5): 507–518.
- Wing, Coady, Seth M Freedman, and Alex Hollingsworth.** 2024. "Stacked difference-in-differences." National Bureau of Economic Research.

Table 1—Event-Study Estimates of the Association Between Gender-Affirming Hormone Therapy (GAHT) and Running Away

	Cohort-specific association				Average association	
	Age 14	Age 15	Age 16	Age 17	Treated share	Equal weight
Association with GAHT	-8.39* (4.64)	-3.37 (2.10)	-2.43 (2.09)	-0.74 (1.56)	-1.97* (1.11)	-3.73*** (1.43)
Pre-treatment mean	8.70	8.62	7.38	11.26	9.68	9.68
Treated individuals	23	58	122	231	434	434
Control individuals	58	122	231	667	1,078	1,078
Sample size	486	1,080	2,118	5,388	9,072	9,072

Notes: * $p < .1$, ** $p < .05$, *** $p < .01$. The table reports event-study estimates of the association between initiating GAHT and running away, shown in the row labeled “Association with GAHT,” with robust standard errors clustered by individual in parentheses. Columns 1–4 present cohort-specific estimates for individuals who initiated GAHT at ages 14 through 17 respectively. The “Treated share” column reports a weighted average in which each cohort is weighted by its share of treated individuals, while the “Equal weight” column reports an unweighted average that assigns equal weight to all cohorts. Regressions control for receipt of puberty blockers, exposure to conversion therapy, and gender-identity milestones (first feeling one’s gender differed from sex assigned at birth, first thinking of oneself as transgender, first disclosure, and living full time in one’s gender). All models include cohort-by-event-time, cohort-by-calendar-year, and cohort-by-individual fixed effects, and synthetic unit weights are applied.

Figure 1. Event-Study Estimates of the Association Between Gender-Affirming Hormone Therapy (GAHT) and Running Away

Notes: See notes for Table 1.